

LOAD HISTORY DEPENDENCE OF GRAPHITE EPOXY JOINTS/REPAIRS: AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

W. K. Chiu¹, S. Galea², R. Jones¹ and S. Pitt¹

¹ *Department of Mechanical Engineering, Monash University,
Wellington Rd, Clayton, Vic 3168, Australia.*

² *Airframes and Engines Division, Aeronautical Research Laboratory, Defense Science and
Technology Organisation, 506 Lorimer St, Pt Melbourne, Victoria, 3207, Australia.*

SUMMARY: This paper presents the results of an experimental study into the load history dependence of adhesively bonded joints and therefore, by analogy, adhesively bonded repairs. Here attention is focused on the effects of rate dependence on the failure loads of graphite epoxy scarf joints as well as double and single lap joints. This test program has revealed that, when evaluating the structural integrity and durability of composite joints or bonded repairs, it may be necessary to take load history effects into account. In this test program it was found that increasing the loading rate can either raise or lower the failure load depending on the nature of the joint (or repair). This work also illustrates the need to consider interlaminar failure in the design process and highlights the fact that, designs based on rate independent analyses cannot automatically be assumed to be conservative.

KEYWORDS: bonded joints, composite repairs, failure loads, experimental testing, certification

INTRODUCTION

The island continent of Australia is heavily dependent on transportation and the associated infra-structure for its economic survival. During the post war years Australia experienced rapid economic growth. In this period much of Australia's current infra-structure was constructed. However, there are now doubts on its durability and structural integrity. Economic and market forces have also resulted in utilization of structures beyond their original design life. In the international sphere a number of high visibility aviation accidents have served as a trigger for government and industry action. This "tombstone activity" was largely due to a series of incidents; viz:

- 1) The 1975 Eastern Airlines Flight 66 accident at JFK International which resulted in 113 fatalities;
- 2) The PSA mid-air collision in San Diego in 1978. This resulted in 144 fatalities;
- 3) The Aloha Airlines incident in 1988 which resulted in 1 fatality.

The Aloha incident revealed a number of fundamental weaknesses both in structural design and maintenance. Failure was due to the presence of multiple (interacting) cracks in neighbouring locations, this is now referred to as Multi Site Damage (MSD), coupled with

corrosion damage. Indeed, subsequent investigations have also revealed that multiple mechanical repairs, in close proximity, can also compromise structural integrity.

In the aeronautical scene Australia has developed unique methods which utilize externally bonded composite patches to repair cracked, or damaged, structural components [1]. Although this repair methodology was first used to repair cracks in military aircraft it has recently been applied to civilian aircraft. The application to Boeing 727, 767 and 747 aircraft is described in [2, 3], which outline a series of flight demonstrator programs.

When certifying composite joints and repairs a knowledge of the potential failure mechanisms of composite repairs is mandatory. For bonded joints and composite repairs, failure of the matrix material, i.e. interlaminar failure, often drives the design process, see [4]. From the structural/design view point the necessity of transmitting the load via an adhesive bond, from the composite to the underlying or connecting structure often results in matrix dominated interlaminar shearing forces. Indeed, this was recognised as one of the primary causes of the disbonding of the structural reinforcement of the F111C wing pivot fitting [4, 5, 6]. This failure, which is documented in [4], did not occur instantaneously, upon commencement of the strain hold, but took a significant time to occur. As a result of this failure mechanism attention was subsequently focused on understanding, and thereby preventing, this interlaminar failure process, see [4, 5, 6]. To this end it was recently shown [7, 8] that, for adhesively bonded joints, neglecting the time dependent nature of the stress-strain curves can result in fictitious values for the stresses and strains in the joint. Given the potential importance of this phenomena, i.e. load history dependence of the failure loads, the present paper addresses the question;

Can the non-linear time dependent stress strain response of both the adhesive and the matrix material be reflected by load history dependent failure loads?

SPECIMEN DESCRIPTION

The experimental tests were performed using nine specimens made from graphite fibers and an epoxy resin, viz: (AS4/3501). This material combination is widely in use in both the aircraft industry and in general engineering. For the geometrical layout a scarf joint specimen was chosen which was typical of that used in the wing skin of a modern fighter aircraft, and also in classical (i.e. traditional) composite repairs to composites. The adhesive for the scarf joint was FM300-2 with an approximate layer thickness of 0.2mm. All specimens were clamped in an area 100 mm from each end. The geometry of the specimen was as shown in Figure 1, and the working (test) area was approximately 250 mm. The symmetric adherend(s) consisted of 50 plies with a $[(+45_2, -45_2, 0_4)_3, 90]_s$ ply configuration. Each graphite/epoxy doubler consisted of 16 plies with a $[0_2, +45, -45, -45, +45, 0_2]_s$ ply configuration.

To establish quality of the fabrication process the specimens were C scanned using a 2.5 MHz probe, which was located a distance of 64 mm from the specimens. Except for specimen 8 the scan-images of the nine scarf joint (repair) specimens revealed an acceptable bond quality. This specimen had a major disbond, or delamination, within the scarf joint (i.e. repair). Consequently, Specimen 8 was used as a dummy specimen. This defect subsequently led to a reduced failure load.

To enable the strains to be recorded two gauges were bonded on each specimen. One was located on the center of the patch and the other on the “coupon” material remote from the doubler. The strain gauges used were 5mm self-temperature-compensated gauges with a resistance of 350 Ohm and had a gauge factor of 2.105.

One objective of the test program was to establish the effect of load history on the failure load of the specimens. To investigate this aspect the specimens were loaded under load control an Instron testing machine, using hydraulic grips. The chosen load ramps were approximately 0.01 KN/s, 0.1KN/s, 10KN/s and 1000KN/s. To guarantee the repeatability of the experiments each load rate test was performed with two specimens. Preliminary tests revealed a catastrophic failure and it impossible to detect the location of failure initiation. Consequently, to observe the failure process a high speed video camera (time window 20 sec, 12,000 picture per second) was installed, for tests on specimen 2 and 3. The remaining specimen, specimen number 9, was used to perform a creep tests at 95 kN, 105 kN, 110 kN, 113 kN and 120 kN with load ramps of ≈ 0.01 kN/s.

Figure 1: Geometry of the scarf joint specimen

A PC was used to tune an appropriate sample rate and to store the data points. The data acquisition unit recorded the applied load, the actuator displacement and the two strain gauge readings using. The load and displacement values during the tests were provided by the data unit of the tensile testing machine. The strain gauge readings were collected using a self-temperature compensated quarter-bridge. The resultant failure loads are shown in Table 1.

Unfortunately, even at low loading rates, the failure of the specimens was catastrophic, i.e. without any pre-warnings prior to the sudden failure. It was impossible to observe the precise location where the failure initiated. Consequently, a high-speed camera with a picture sequence of 12,000 images per second was used while testing specimens 2 and 3. The resultant images for Specimen number 2 are shown in the Figure 2. In both cases it was apparent that the failure initiated at the patch-coupon interface area. Unfortunately, the resolution of the camera was such that it was not possible to ascertain whether the failure was initiated in the adhesive or in the graphite epoxy adherends.

Following this test program specimen 9 was used to perform a creep test. The specimen was initially loaded slowly ($\approx 0.01\text{kN/s}$) to approximately 95 kN and the load then held for 700 seconds. The specimen was then loaded slowly, at approximately the same loading rate, to approximately 105 kN and the loads held for 800 seconds. Further load holds were performed at 110kN for ≈ 800 seconds, at 114kN for ≈ 1300 seconds and at 120 kN for approximately ≈ 1300 seconds with no apparent creep, or failure, at any of these load holds. Indeed, the test was terminated when after reaching 120kN the specimen had not failed.

Table 1: Summary of Experimental Results

Specimen No.	Loading Rate kN/s	Sample Rate (Hz)	Strain Centre $\mu\epsilon$	Strain Remote $\mu\epsilon$	Failure Load
1	915	1000	1788	3205	84.8
2	800	1000	1614	2847	94.8
3	765	1000	2292	3057	83.3
4	9.7	50	2718	4434	114.2
5	0.125	5	3151	4733	111.5
6	0.1	5	3033	3911	102.5
7	0.012	1	2935	4729	115.0
8 ⁺ Dummy	0.096 Specimen	0.5 used	2609 to set up	3313 the test	93.8 program

⁺ This specimen, had been used as a dummy to calibrate the test rig prior to performing the final test program. It also contained an obvious flaw.

DISCUSSION

The load displacement and the load strain results obtained for each of the nine scarf joint repair specimens were essentially linear to failure. However, the failure loads decreased as the loading rate increased. The range was from 83.3 kN at high load rates to 115.0 kN at low loading rates (or to >120 kN if the results of specimen 9 are included). Indeed, the ratio of the maximum failure load, at low loading rates, to the minimum failure load, at high loading rates, was approximately 1.39. This infers that when designing composite joints the role of rate dependent response of the composite adherends may need to be considered.

The location of the failure initiation was dominantly in the “patch transition area”, i.e. away from the scarf joint. Unfortunately the failure surfaces were such that it was not possible to

determine the exact failure location. A detailed inspection of the failed specimens indicated that the failure surface appeared to jump between the matrix material and the adhesive bond.

Figure 2: Failure initiation of scarf joint specimen 2 (frame 3)

THE FAILURE OF ADHESIVELY BONDED LAP JOINTS

To further evaluate this effect a series of 8 tests were performed on both single and double, i.e. symmetric, graphite epoxy (AS4/3501) lap joints with loading rates of 0.01, 0.1, 10.0 and 100kN/s. The double lap joints were as shown in Figure 3, with the lower adherend consisting of 8 plies with a ply configuration of $[(+ 45,- 45)_{2S}]_S$ and an upper adherend of $[(+ 45,- 45)_{2S}]_S$ bonded with a single layer of FM300. The single lap joints had the same upper adherends but the lower adherend was $[(+ 45,- 45)_{2S}]_S$, i.e the upper and lower adherends were identical. The specimens had a working section 175 mm long and 40 mm wide, whilst the gripped area was 40 mm x 40 mm and the (bonded) overlap was 25 mm long, see Figure 3. Typical experimental load displacement curves for the double and single lap joints are shown in Figures 4 and 5 respectively.

In both cases we see that, as in the scarf joints, the failure loads and displacement were significantly effected by the loading rates. In contrast to the previous tests, on the scarf joint, increasing the rate of loading increased the failure load and decreased the displacement at failure. Unlike the scarf joint specimens the failure appeared to initiate in the graphite epoxy, see Figure 3, and, in general, left a layer of the upper adherend attached to the lower

adherend. This failure mechanism has previously been discussed in [4, 10, 11] and is common to both composite repairs and step lap joints. Indeed, this was the failure mechanism found in the F/A-18 step lap joint test program, see [9].

No Bending about the center line

Figure 3. Typical geometry for symmetric lap joint tests.

Figure 4. Load displacement results for double lap joint specimens

Figure 5. Load displacement results for single lap joint specimens

CONCLUSION

This test program has revealed that when evaluating the structural integrity and durability of composite joints or bonded repairs, see [10, 11] for an aerospace perspective, it may be necessary to take load history effects into account. The results of this experimental study support the conclusions outlined in [7, 8] that for adhesively bonded composite joints and composite repairs current design strategies may need to be extended in order to cater for this observed effect. In this context the present test program has shown that increasing the loading rate can either raise or lower the failure load depending on the nature of the joint (or repair). Hence, designs based on rate independent analyses cannot be assumed to be conservative. It also illustrates the need to consider interlaminar failure in the design process.

REFERENCES

1. Baker A. A. and Jones R., Bonded Repair of Aircraft Structure, Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, The Hague, 1988.
2. Bartholomeus R., Paul J. J. and Roberts J. D., Application of bonded composite Repair technology to Civilian Aircraft- 747 Demonstrator Program, Proceedings International Conference on Aircraft Damage Assessment and Repair, Edited by R. Jones and N. J. Miller, Published by The Institution of Engineers Australia, ISBN (BOOK) 85825 537 5, July 1991.
3. Jones R., "Recent Developments in Repair Technology", Proceedings Int. Conference on Aircraft Damage Assessment and Repair, Published by The Institution of Engineers, Australia, ISBN 85825-537-5, pp. 76-84, 1991.

4. Jones R., Chiu W. K. and Hanna S., Potential failure mechanisms of bonded composite repairs for metal and concrete, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics*, 21, 107-119, 1994.
5. Jones R., Molent L., Paul J. J. , Saunders T., Chiu W. K., "Development of a composite repair and the associated inspection intervals for the F111C stiffener runout region", In *NASA Conference Publication 3274*, pp.339-350, 1994.
6. Molent L., Callinan R. J. and Jones R., "Design of an all boron epoxy doubler for the F-111C wing pivot fitting: Structural aspects", *Journal of Composite Structures*, 11, 1, pp. 57-83, 1989.
7. Jones R. , Tripit B., Chiu W. K. and Tomas J., "Lap joint theory revisited", *Journal of Polymers and Polymer Composites*, 1995, vol 3, 1, pp 11-19.
8. Chao M. Chiu , W. K., Jones R., Wang J., and Kelly D., "The Analysis of Bonded Lap Joints", *Proceedings ICCM11*, Australia, (in press).
9. van Blaricum T., Bates P. and Jones R., "An experimental investigation into the effect of impact damage on the compressive strength of step lap joints", *Journal of Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 32, 5, 667-674, 1989.
10. Jones R. and Smith R., "Continued Airworthiness Of Composite Repairs To Primary Structures For Military Aircraft", *Proceedings 6th Australian Aeronautical Conference*, pp 311-316, 20-23 March, 1995, published by The Institution of. Engineers Australia, NCP 95/1, ISBN (Book) 0 85825 624 X.
11. Jones R., Chiu W. K. and Smith R., "Airworthiness of composite repairs: Failure mechanisms", *Engineering Failure Analysis*, 2, 2, 117- 128, 1995.